

README – Raw Data Upload for

Diketo[*n*]CPPs as Chiral and Shape-adaptive Fullerene Hosts and Precursors to DBP[*n*]CPPs

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The following raw data of various analytical techniques and quantum chemical calculations are compressed into a single .zip file. The files for each compound are sorted in a folder structure, where each method has its own folder. The names (or numbers) of the molecules follow the numbering scheme from the article. The files and file types are as follows for each method.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR)

Raw data (Bruker) in the original folder structure, with folder named according to the respective NMR experiment

Mass Spectroscopy (MS).

docx file or .pdf file with the output of the MS software.

Ultraviolet and Visible Light Spectroscopy (UV/Vis).

txt files with the wavelength (nm) extinction coefficient (ϵ)

Fluorescence spectra and Fluorescence titration

txt file or .asc file with the recorded fluorescence intensity data. .qua files with quantum yield measurements.

High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)

.pdf file with the chromatograms and analysis reports from the HPLC software.

Electronic circular dichroism (ECD) and circularly polarized luminescence (CPL)

.txt files containing the wavelength (nm) vs. ellipticity (mdeg) data. .xlsx files with the emission wavelength-dependent luminescence intensity and dissymmetry factor (g_{lum}) values.

Density Functional Theory (DFT) Calculations

Turbomole calculations

.xyz coordinate files on the PBEh-3c level of theory

ridft.out for the Turbomole ridft single point calculations with orbital energies (B3LYP-D3BJ/def2-TZVP)

escf.out for the Turbomole TDDFT calculations with the vertical excitation energies (B3LYP-D3BJ/def2-TZVP)

.cub files for the calculated orbitals on the cubic 3D grid (named as relative position to the frontier orbitals and orbital number i.e.)

Gaussian Calculations

.log files from Gaussian single-point or geometry optimization calculations, containing energy, frequency, and orbital information(B3LYP-D3BJ/6-31g(d))

.chk or .fchk files for post-processing (e.g., population analysis or orbital visualization).

xtb Calculations

out files from xtb semiempirical calculations, including optimized geometries, energies, and thermochemical data;

.xyz files for final structures.

StrainViz Analysis

Output folders containing .tcl or .txt files with the strain energy components